

SYNTHESIS OF NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART III

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Piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-, -4-methyl-, -5-methyl-, -6-methyl-, -4-chloro-, -6-chloro-, -4-ethoxy-benzothiazoles and their hydrochlorides have been synthesised and their local anaesthetic activity has been tested. The pharmacological screening has shown that the hydrochloride of piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-6-methylbenzothiazole is the most potent of all the compounds described here.

In continuation of the previous work on local anaesthetics (Bhargava and Nair, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 42) and 2-aminobenzothiazoles (Bhargava and Baliga, *ibid.*, 1958, 35, 807), it was considered worthwhile to prepare 2-aminobenzothiazole, 2-amino-4-methyl-, -5-methyl-, -6-methyl-, -4-chloro-, -6-chloro- and -4-ethoxy-benzothiazoles according to the method of Hugershoff (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3121) and to convert these respectively into piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-, -4-methyl-, -5-methyl-, -6-methyl-, -4-chloro-, -6-chloro- and -4-ethoxy-benzothiazoles, firstly by condensation with chloroacetyl chloride and secondly with piperidine according to Bhargava and Nair (*loc. cit.*). The hydrochlorides of these bases have been prepared and their local anaesthetic activity has been tested.

A study of the pharmacological screening, in accordance with the procedure adopted by Bulbring and Wajda (*J. Pharmacol.*, 1945, 85, 78), has shown that the hydrochloride of piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-6-methylbenzothiazole is the most successful local anaesthetic out of the six compounds tested and is the most potent compound amongst the methyl derivatives prepared. The hydrochlorides of piperidinoacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole, piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-chlorobenzothiazole and piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole produced good plexus anaesthesia in frogs. Piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-methylbenzothiazol and piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-ethoxy-benzothiazole hydrochlorides also showed good anaesthetic action. It is interesting to note that all these compounds took less time for the onset of anaesthesia than procaine hydrochloride, the standard substance used.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Aminobenzothiazoles were prepared according to the method of Hugershoff (*loc. cit.*). Their properties and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

[B denotes bezothiazole. A denotes 2-amino.]

Compounds.	%Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1. A-B ^a	.. 75	129°	C ₇ H ₆ N ₂ S	20.78	21.33
2. A-4-methyl-B ^b	.. 68	136°	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ S	19.12	19.51
3. A-5-methyl-B ^c	.. 69	143°	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ S	19.01	19.51
4. A-6-methyl-B	.. 73	138°	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ S	19.20	19.51
5. A-4-chloro-B ^c	.. 75	202°	C ₇ H ₅ N ₂ ClS	16.84	17.34
6. A-6-chloro-B	.. 67	198°	C ₇ H ₅ N ₂ ClS	16.92	17.34
7. A-4-ethoxy-B	.. 51	197°	C ₉ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	16.10	16.49

a Hugershoff, *loc. cit.*

b Hunter *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1385.

c Bhargava and Baliga, *loc. cit.*

Chloroacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole.—Chloroacetyl chloride (2.5 c.c.), dissolved in pure benzene (10 c.c.), was gradually added to 2-aminobenzothiazole (5 g.), dissolved in benzene (30 c.c.). The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° on a water-bath for 1½ hours. Benzene was distilled off and the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and then dried. The product was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 156°, yield 4.5 g.

Similarly chloroacetyl derivatives of other 2-aminobenzothiazoles were prepared. Their properties and analytical data are mentioned in Table II.

TABLE II

Compounds.	% Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1. Chloroacetyl-A-B	58	156	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ ClS	14.02	14.13
2. Chloroacetyl-A-4-methyl-B	70	180	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	13.00	13.30
3. Chloroacetyl-A-5-methyl-B	80	185	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	12.99	13.30
4. Chloroacetyl-A-6-methyl-B	70	183	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	13.12	13.30
5. Chloroacetyl-A-4-chloro-B	62	187	C ₉ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	12.01	12.26
6. Chloroacetyl-A-6-chloro-B	69	202	C ₉ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	11.98	12.26
7. Chloroacetyl-A-4-ethoxy-B	75	185	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	11.90	11.83

Piperidinoacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole.—To chloroacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole (4 g.), dissolved in absolute ethanol (40 c.c.), piperidine (4 c.c.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 4 to 5 hours. Alcohol and excess of piperidine were recovered by distillation and the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate to remove the acid impurities and finally with water. The product was crystallised from 80% alcohol and recrystallised from benzene in yellow crystals, m.p. 85°, yield 3g.

Similarly piperidinoacetyl derivatives of other 2-aminobenzothiazoles were prepared. Their hydrochlorides were also prepared as usual and crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture (1:1). The properties and analytical data of these derivatives are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

* Compounds.	% Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	Piperidinoacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazoles.		Hydrochlorides.		
				% Sulphur.		M.P.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
1.	50	85°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	11.58	11.63	248°	11.10	11.40
2.	58	145°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	11.00	11.07	235°	10.60	10.90
3.	45	120°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	10.98	11.07	..	..	..
4.	50	90°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	11.12	11.07	253°	10.41	10.90
5.	72	130°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ ON ₂ ClS	10.20	10.34	227°	9.98	10.26
6.	54	172°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ ON ₂ ClS	10.28	10.34	256°	9.82	10.26
7.	75	135°	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.98	10.03	239°	9.86	9.98

* Piperidinoacetyl derivatives compounds as recorded in Table I.

Pharmacological Test : Plexus Anæsthesia in Frogs.—Hydrochloride solutions, 0.1% and 0.2%, were used and the time of onset of anæsthesia was recorded and compared with that of procaine hydrochloride as a standard substance. The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Hydrochloride of piperidinoacetyl—,	With 0.1% solution for onset of anaesthesia in		With 0.2% solution for onset of anaesthesia in	
	0.1N-HCl. 0.2N-HCl.		0.1N-HCl. 0.2N-HCl.	
1. *Procaine hydrochloride	35.0 mins.	43.0 mins.	32.0 mins.	41.5 mins.
2. -A-B	24.0	29.0	20.5	26.0
3. -A-4-methyl-B	13.5	17.5	11.5	14.5
4. -A-6-methyl-B	9.5	12.0	6.5	8.0
5. -A-4-chloro-B	23.5	33.5	23.5	31.5
6. -A-6-chloro-B	18.5	26.5	18.0	24.0
7. -A-4-ethoxy-B	11.5	16.0	11.5	14.5

It was used as such and not in the form of piperidino derivative.

The study of the pharmacological screening has shown that the hydrochloride of piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-6-methylbenzothiazole is the most active of all the compounds described here and also among the three methyl-substituted derivatives. Piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-ethoxybenzothiazole and piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-methylbenzothiazole hydrochlorides follow it next in order of pharmacological activity. It is all the more interesting to find that the hydrochlorides of piperidinoacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazoles described require less time for the onset of anaesthesia than the standard substance, procaine hydrochloride, used.

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